

1 such as electrical resistance or back EMF [1], since due to their influence, the motor's
2 characteristics, and hence its performance, during operation are not the same as those
3 considered during design [2]. Real-time knowledge of temperature in the various motor
4 parts is also very useful in order to predict incipient failures and to adopt corrective
5 actions, thus obtaining not only better control but higher reliability of the electrical
6 machine.

7 In fact, the early prediction of thermal aging, which makes insulations vulnerable, as well
8 as of other thermal factors directly influencing motor health and life can avoid dangerous
9 failures [3-5]. The main causes of thermal faults are: overloads [6], cyclic mode [7], over
10 voltage and/or voltage unbalances [8], distortions [4], thermal insulation aging [3],
11 obstructed or impaired cooling [9], poor design and manufacture [3], and skin effect [10].

12 For several years, great efforts have been devoted to the temperature and speed
13 measurement of electrical machines, and several methods for temperature [11-13] and
14 speed measurements [14] have already been proposed in the literature. While the direct
15 measurement of temperature in electric DC machines is a long-established approach [13-
16 15], some authors obtained the average winding temperature from the resistance
17 measurement [13]. A more modern method can be found in [12,16], but the temperature
18 measurement gave rise to two major problems: optimum sensor placement and the
19 difficulty of achieving rotor thermal measurements. Likewise, speed measurement can
20 also be difficult [17]. Moreover, information from sensors installed on rotating parts leads
21 to techno-economic difficulties in the measurement chain. Sensorless solutions have
22 therefore been considered by many studies [16,18-20].

23 One of the first examples of temperature estimation was presented in [21], where a
24 Luenberger observer was applied both to a DC rolling mill motor and a squirrel cage

1 induction motor. Another solution was described in [22] where the authors used a steady-
2 state Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) associated with its transient version. To estimate the
3 resistance some authors combine EKF with a smooth variable structure filter [23]. Some
4 research on bi-estimation has been done [24], which describes and implements an
5 algorithm for combined flux-linkage and position estimation for PM motors based on the
6 machine's characteristic curves. A very interesting approach was proposed in [25],
7 applying and experimentally validating a transient EKF to estimate the speed and
8 armature temperature in a BDC motor. However, EKF has some limitations, in particular:
9 (i) if the system is incorrectly modelled the filter may quickly diverge; (ii) the EKF
10 assumes Gaussian noise [26-28]; (iii) if the initial state estimate values are incorrect the
11 filter may also diverge; (iv) the EKF can be difficult to stabilize due to the sensitivity of
12 the covariance matrices [27,29].

13 To the authors' knowledge, very few publications deal with the simultaneous estimation
14 of speed and armature temperature of DC machines [25], especially when performed by
15 intelligent techniques [29]. Artificial neural networks (ANN) have demonstrated their
16 ability in a wide variety of applications such as process control [30], identification [31],
17 diagnostics [32], pattern recognition [33], robot vision [34], flight scheduling [35],
18 finance and economics [36] and medical diagnosis [37].

19 In this paper, while referring to our previous study [29], in which an estimator based on
20 Multilayer Perceptron with Levenberg-Marquardt BP was developed in order to avoid the
21 limitations of the standard ANN, a solution based on a Cascade-Forward Neural Network
22 (CFNN) and Bayesian Regulation BP (BRBP) is proposed. A highly accurate BRBP-
23 based ANN was proposed in [38,39] but it requires **an extremely long** convergence time,
24 and is in fact known to be among the slowest algorithms to converge. Based on the

1 approach already presented in [29], the purpose of this paper is to propose a novel
2 approach using a learning algorithm which is a compromise between speed and accuracy.
3 The BFGS can respond to these two constraints [39].

4 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the thermal model
5 of the BDC motor, Section 3 discusses ANN and CFNN based on Quasi-Newton BFGS
6 BP, and Section 4 presents the simulation results and analysis. Finally, some conclusions
7 are discussed in Section 5.

8 2. Thermal model of BDC machines

9 Research interest in studying rotating electric machinery from the combined viewpoints
10 of thermal and electrical processes dates back to the 1950s [40,41]. The model used in
11 this paper was proposed by Acarnley and Al-Tayie in [25]. This is a simplified model and
12 is obtained by considering the power dissipation and heat transfer in the BDC machine
13 [25]. The power is dissipated by the armature current flowing through the armature
14 resistance, which varies in proportion to the temperature. The electrical equation of a
15 BDC motor can be written as:

$$16 \quad V_a = R_{a0}(1 + \alpha_{cu}\theta)i_a + L_a \frac{di_a}{dt} + k_e\omega \quad (1)$$

17 where V_a (V) is the armature voltage, R_{a0} (Ω) is the armature resistance at ambient
18 temperature, α_{cu} ($\alpha_{cu} = 0.004 \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$) is the temperature coefficient of resistance, θ ($^\circ\text{C}$) the
19 temperature above ambient, i_a (A) the armature current, L_a (H) the armature inductance,
20 k_e (V/rad/s) the torque constant, and ω (rad/s) the armature speed.

21 The mechanical equation of a BDC motor can be written as:

$$22 \quad J \frac{d\omega}{dt} + b\omega + T_l = k_e i_a \quad (2)$$

23 where J ($\text{kg}\times\text{m}^2$) is total inertia, b ($\text{N}\times\text{m}\times\text{s}$) is the viscous friction constant and T_l ($\text{N}\times\text{m}$)
24 is the load torque.

1 The power losses (P_l) include contributions from copper losses and iron losses which are
 2 frequency dependent; the copper loss is proportional to current squared multiplied by
 3 resistance which depends on temperature, while the iron loss is proportional to speed
 4 squared for constant excitation multiplied by the iron loss constant ($k_{ir} = 0.0041$
 5 $W/(rad/s)^2$) [25]:

$$6 \quad P_l = R_{a0} (1 + \alpha_{cu}\theta) i_a^2 + k_{ir}\omega^2 \quad (3)$$

7 Heat flow from the armature surface of the BDC motor is directly to the cooling air and
 8 depends on the thermal transfer coefficients at zero speed ($k_o = 4.33 W/^\circ C$) and at speed
 9 ($k_T = 0.0028 rad/s$); the thermal power flow from the armature surface to the BDC motor
 10 surface is proportional to the temperature difference between the motor and the ambient
 11 temperature. The rate of temperature variation depends on the thermal capacity ($H = 18$
 12 $KJ/^\circ C$), and it is simplified by Acarnley and Al-Tayie in [25] as follows:

$$13 \quad P_l = k_0(I + k_T\omega)\theta + H\frac{d\theta}{dt} \quad (4)$$

14 By arranging the previous Eqs., we can write the system of equations as:

$$15 \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{di_a}{dt} &= -\frac{R_{a0}(1 + \alpha_{cu}\theta)}{L_a} i_a - \frac{k_e}{L_a} \omega + \frac{1}{L_a} v_a \\ \frac{d\omega}{dt} &= \frac{k_e}{J} - \frac{b}{J} \omega - \frac{K}{J} T_l \\ \frac{d\theta}{dt} &= \frac{R_{a0}(1 + \alpha_{cu}\theta)}{H} i_a^2 + \frac{k_{ir}}{H} \omega^2 - \frac{k_0(1 + k_T\omega)}{H} \theta \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

16 3. ANN estimator

17 In recent years, CFNNs have become a widely used back propagation algorithm [42-51]
 18 and have proved their capability in several applications [49-57] and have proved their
 19 capability in several applications [49-57]. CFNNs are similar to feed-forward neural
 20 networks (FFNNs), but include a weight connection from the input to each layer and from
 21 each layer to the successive layers [49-56]. For example, a four-layer network has
 22 connections from layer 1 to layer 2, layer 2 to layer 3, layer 3 to layer 4, layer 1 to layer

1 3, layer 1 to layer 4 and layer 2 to layer 4. In addition, the four-layer network also has
2 connections between input and all layers. FFNNs and CFNNs can potentially learn any
3 input-output relationship, but CFNNs with more layers **might** learn complex relationships
4 more quickly [50-53], making them the right choice for accelerated learning in ANNs
5 [51]. The results obtained by **Filik and Kurban** in [52] suggest that CFNN BP can be more
6 effective than FFNN BP in some cases.

7 **In the present study, after solving equation (5), a random white Gaussian noise was added**
8 **to the inputs and outputs of the BDC machine model. The outputs of the model were then**
9 **used as the CFNN target and its inputs as the CFNN inputs, as shown in Figure 1. This**
10 **noise makes the training very slow, but the CFNN is well trained and applicable in real-**
11 **time, also is used to track the performance and robustness of the CFNN. The half of the**
12 **simulation data of the BDC machine have been used to create training set, the other half**
13 **shared equally by test and validation sets. The procedure used to train the NN was the**
14 **cross-validation error checked over multiple sets of training data.**

15 The BP algorithm was used to form the neural network such that on all training patterns,
16 the sum squared error (E) between the actual network outputs (y) and the corresponding
17 desired outputs (y_d) is minimized to a supposed value:

$$18 \quad E = \sum (y_d - y)^2 \quad (6)$$

19 To obtain the optimal network architecture, for each layer the transfer function types must
20 be determined by a trial and error method. On the input **(2 units)** and three hidden layers
21 **(3, 4 and 5 units)**, a hyperbolic tangent sigmoid transfer function was used, defined as:

$$22 \quad f(net_j) = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2net_j}} - 1 \quad (7)$$

23 where net is the weighted sum of the input unit j , and $f(net)$ is the output units. The output
24 layer has 3 units with a pure linear transfer function, defined as:

$$f(\text{net}_j) = \text{net}_j \quad (8)$$

3.1. Quasi-Newton BFGS BP algorithm

The Quasi-Newton BFGS BP training algorithm is a useful method for updating network weights and biases according to the BFGS formulae [58-61]. The algorithm belongs to the quasi-Newton family and was devised by Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb, and Shanno in 1970 [62-65] to achieve fast optimization [60-61]. It is an iterative method that approximates Newton's method without the inverse of Hessian's matrix [60]. It is a second order optimization algorithm [60-61]. In this paper, the weight and bias values were updated according to the BFGS quasi-Newton method, and the new weight w_{k+1} was computed as:

$$w_{k+1} = \omega_k - H_k^{-1} \Psi_k \quad (9)$$

where: H_k is the Hessian matrix of the performance index at the current values of the weights and biases. When H_k is large, w_{k+1} computation is complex and time consuming [66-68]. BFGS do not calculate the inverse Hessian but approximate it as follows:

$$H_{k+1} = H_k + \frac{y_k y_k^T}{y_k^T S_k} - \frac{H_k S_k S_k^T H_k}{S_k^T H_k S_k} \quad (10)$$

where: $\Psi_k = \nabla f(w_{k+1})$, $S_k = w_{k+1} - \omega_k$ and $y_k = \nabla f(w_{k+1}) - \nabla f(w_k)$. The new formula can be approximated as:

$$w_{k+1} = \omega_k - \left(H_k + \frac{y_k y_k^T}{y_k^T S_k} - \frac{H_k S_k S_k^T H_k}{S_k^T H_k S_k} \right) \Psi_k \quad (11)$$

This method has several advantages: it has a better convergence rate than using conjugate gradients [58-61], it is stable because the BFGS Hessian update is symmetric and positive definite [60], and BFGS computes an approximation to the inverse Hessian in only $O(n^2)$ operations [60]. However, this method requires a lot of memory to converge, especially

1 on a large scale [66-69], whereas many researchers are interested in how to reduce
2 memory needs [67-71].

3 **4. Simulation results**

4 Figures 2 to 5 show the simulation result of the simultaneous estimation of speed,
5 armature temperature and resistance by CFNN based on BFGS BP for a continuous
6 running duty or abbreviated by duty type S1. Duty type S1 is characterized by operation
7 at a constant load maintained for a sufficient time to allow the machine to reach thermal
8 equilibrium [72]. The ANN outputs are in good agreement with the model outputs as can
9 be seen below, proving the ability of the proposed approach. The BDC motor parameters
10 used during simulations are as follows:

- 11 - Rated voltage $V_a = 240$ V
- 12 - Rated power $P = 3$ kW
- 13 - Rated torque $T_l = 11$ Nm
- 14 - Armature resistance $R_{a0} = 3.5$ Ω
- 15 - Armature inductance $L_a = 34$ mH.

16 The estimated speed and the corresponding errors are shown in Figure 2. The results
17 obtained by Acarnley and Al-Tayie in [25] suggest that the speed estimation error from
18 EKF is approximately 2%. Moreover, it is not suitable for high-performance servo drives
19 [25]. However, in the results obtained here, the error is less than 0.4 rad/s and represents
20 only 0.18% of the final value, as shown in Figure 5. The estimated temperature and the
21 corresponding errors are shown in Figure 3 where it reaches 79.5 °C, while the model
22 output is 80 °C and the steady state estimated error is less than 0.5 °C. This is insignificant
23 and represents only 0.625% as can be seen from Figures 3 and 5. This can be contrasted
24 with the results in [25] which suggested that the temperature estimation error was 3 °C,

1 i.e. approximately 3.75%, while Nestler and Sattler in [21] found that the estimated
2 winding temperature error was high. Even though Pantonial et al. in [22] reported an
3 improvement, estimating that the error did not exceed 1 °C, the results presented in this
4 paper are the best. Figure 4 depicts the resistance estimated by CFNN based on BFGS BP
5 and the model response. It can be seen from this Figure that the resistance has the same
6 curvature as the armature temperature, where the steady state estimated resistance is 4.59
7 Ω , i.e. less than 6×10^{-3} of the simulated resistance. Practically, this difference is a
8 negligible quantity and represents only 0.13% of the final value. The results obtained are
9 more precise than those presented in [23]. Figure 5 shows the estimation errors of speed,
10 temperature and resistance, and their percentage in relation to their rated value. Figure 5
11 and Table show more clearly the good agreement between the model outputs and the
12 outputs of our intelligent sensor. The simulation results can be summarized by the
13 following Table:

14 **5. Conclusion**

15 A sensorless simultaneous estimator for BDC machines based on a CFNN trained by
16 BFGS BP has been proposed and verified through simulation and by comparison with
17 earlier studies. The estimator includes sensorless speed estimation, average armature
18 temperature and resistance estimations based only on the voltage and the current
19 measurements. Estimated speed and temperature eliminate the need for speed
20 measurements and the need for a thermal sensor. In addition, estimated temperature
21 solves the problem of obtaining thermal information from the rotating armature.
22 Furthermore, the estimated temperature can be used for a new thermal monitoring
23 method, motor protection, and other duty types since the model includes the load effect
24 in the copper loss and the frequency effect in the iron loss. The estimated resistance can

1 be used to improve the accuracy of the control algorithms which are affected by an
2 increase in resistance as a function of temperature. **Consequently, a sensorless**
3 **simultaneous estimation of speed, temperature, and resistance could be a promising**
4 **research field for future research. The good agreement between model and intelligent**
5 **estimator results demonstrates the efficiency of the proposed approach.**

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15 Table. Summary of the estimation errors.

	$X_{\text{model}} - X_{\text{Estimate}}$	$(X_{\text{model}} - X_{\text{Estimate}}) / X_{\text{model}}$
Speed	0.4 rad/s	0.18%
Temperature	0.5 °C	0.625%
Resistance	0.006 Ω	0.13%

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Figure 1. Estimating system of BDC machine by ANN based on BFGS BP

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Figure 2. Estimated and simulated speed.

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Figure 3. Estimated and simulated armature temperature.

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Figure 4. Estimated and simulated armature resistance.

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Figure 5. Speed, temperature and resistance estimation errors